

Tunneling Fundamentals, Practice and Innovations

Annual Short Course

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Feasibility Study of the Future Extension of the Eisenhower-Johnson Memorial Tunnel

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Research Questions

- EJMT is over capacity and needs additional throughput
- CDOT wants to know where to put a new tunnel
- Research question: How do you select the best tunnel alignment through a given area based on uncertain data?
- Tasks:
 - Gather available data
 - Characterize uncertainty
 - Select plausible alignments
 - Score/rank plausible alignments based on a quantitative assessment of feasibility with uncertainty

Digitization

Courtesy of Ashton Krajnovich

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Historical Ground Classification

<u>Rock Class</u>	<u>Description</u>
Ia Ib	Massive to slightly blocky, no alteration, joint spacing 1.0 feet or greater
IIa IIb	Moderately blocky, little or no alteration, joint spacing 0.5 feet or greater
IIIa IIIb	Very blocky, moderately to highly altered, joint spacing less than 1.0 feet
IVa	Highly crushed and altered, non-plastic, abundant clay, joint spacing less than 0.5 feet
IVb	Plastic, highly altered, squeezing or swelling ground, mainly clay gouge.

("b" indicating the poorer rock within the type)

- DECOMPOSITION & ALTERATION
- WATER ZONES
- JOINT SPACING
- BLOCKY &/or SEAMY

Courtesy of CDOT

Conversion to RMR, Q, and GSI

Direct Conversion

- Simplistic
- High scatter
- Range estimate at best
 - e.g. 1a → RMR 80-100

Indirect/Parameter Conversion

- More work
- More precise
- Better grasp of uncertainty
- Probabilistic distribution of rock mass classification

Courtesy of Hui Lu
Underlying chart from Cai et al. (2004)

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Preliminary Results

RMR value along the main tunnel alignment by parameter conversion

Next Steps:

Validation

Cross-correlation

Inclusion in 3D model

EJMT Research Project Workflow

Material Parameters – Silver Plume Granite

Material Parameters – Idaho Springs Formation

Data from USGS (1974)
and current research

Material Parameters – Fault Gouge

Data from USBR (Cohen, 1971)

Material Parameters – Fault Gouge

Data from USBR (Cohen, 1971)

Material Parameters – Fault Gouge

Data from USBR (1971)

EJMT Aerial View

Legend

- Continental Divide
- Portal

West Portal

East Portal

Potential Portal Locations

- Binary Factors
 - Environmental non-starters
 - Minimum clearance to existing infrastructure
 - Practical geometric design considerations
- Ranking Considerations
 - Environmental concerns
 - Constructability
 - Cut-and-cover length

Eliminate fatally
flawed options

Advance best
options

Potential Alignments

- Assume straight alignments
- $N_{\text{west portals}} \times N_{\text{east portals}} = N_{\text{alignments}}$
- Binary Factors
 - Grade
 - Geometric conflicts
- Ranking Considerations
 - Length
 - Rock mass classification

Side Calculations

- Model existing tunnels → current FoS
- Model parallel and skew bores to determine minimum clearance
- Ground reaction curves
 - Fault gouge, ISF, SPG (vary GSI)
 - Varying overburden
- Support Characteristic Curves
 - Find required liner strength
 - Range of possible stiffnesses
- Generate library of support classes

Cross-Sections

- Shape
 - Circle
 - Poly-Arc
- Size
 - Single-track rail
 - Double-track rail
 - Two-lane vehicular

CDOT (2011)

Figure 28-1-3. Single-Track Railway Tunnels
AREMA (1983)

CDOT (2011)

Alignment/Cross-Section Ranking

- Assign support classes along plausible alignments
- Sum (or side-by-side?)
 - Portal score
 - Total volume
 - Support class
- Order tunnels by rank
- Evaluate trends in results

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